

Changing Technology and Learning Practices in School Education

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Abstract:

Technology has occupied all spheres of human life. School education and learning practices are not untouched from digital technological change. This paper discusses the wholistic approach of digital technology in learning practices in school. The vision for all round development of child will remain incomplete in the absence of wholistic effort taken by school. After introduction of ICT in school education has observed increase in the use of technology in teaching learning process, many teachers from government and private school have started use of technology in their classrooms, but this remained limited with the individual teacher. It could not convert as the school ecosystem. In present arena when the Artificial intelligence (AI) has emerged as the future of learning process. There will be new challenges for learning practices in school education as there are changes in digital technology. This paper examines the 'Digital Technological Approach (DTA)' in school education as the requirement made for "shift from rote learning to real understanding" (NEP, 2020).

Keywords: Digital Technology (DT), ICT, Artificial Intelligence (AI), School Ecosystem.

Introduction:

Any technology exists primarily to make life easier for people. Knowledge societies concerned in knowing how to find, create, process, convert, share, and use information to create and apply knowledge for human advancement (UNESCO, 2005). The data processing and logic capabilities of digital technologies are enabled through microprocesses that are programmed to perform various functions (Johnston et al., 2022). A base-two process is digital technology. Bits, often known as combinations of the digits 0 and 1, are used to represent words and other text-based objects in binary code, which is used to store digital information. Huge volumes of information can be condensed using digital technology and stored on compact storage devices that are simple to preserve and move. Speeds of data transmission have been increased via digitization. People now communicate, learn, and work in a variety of ways. This all credit goes to digital technology (Johnston et al., 2022).

Today digital technology has become the integral part of our life. The term "digital technology" describes the handling, storing, and transmission of data and information via digital systems and electronic gadgets. Social media platforms, e-commerce, online gaming, and online education are just a few examples of the diverse applications of digital technology.

The shift in pedagogical approach:

Traditional method of teaching learning focused on textbook and teachers' experiences. Introduction of government initiatives like, operation blackboard, TLM (now called LTM) and SSA, RMSA promoted the use of teaching aid in classroom processes. With the recommendations received time to time from commissions and curriculum framework for school education and teacher education the few changes have been made in pedagogical approach. The approach has been

changed from teacher centric to learner centric classroom processes. Learners' context taken as reference point while transaction of text. Due to fast and vast change in the technology and society school education is facing challenges of upgrading with latest versions of learning technology.

Digital technology & Blended Learning

Mostly digital platforms are considered as a supportive medium to be used with face-to-face classes. The digital technology for school education is used to address issues untouched due to human limitations ex. Use of graphic to explain about interior of the Earth, biological growth of human and other animals.

In some circumstances like covid-19 situation digital technology has shown that the digital platforms are effective for learning. School children and people from different occupations were depended on online interaction with their school and company. Teacher conducted online classes to engage students. Children also could connect with their school through online classes. Digital technology could connect school children with rest of the world. This also control the psycho-social issues aroused from isolation.

Effective for wholistic Pedagogy: Many teachers on their level uses technology. They use computer, and other digital mediums but this effort remain limited with the individual classroom. Digital pedagogy approach is mostly generalised as use of power point presentation. As it is said before, the digital technology is combination of online as well as offline digital resources. It is the blending of kinds of digital technologies available in local. Apart from power point presentation there is need to use various offline and online digital tools available for concept development. Education technology should be used to provide new opportunities which will be helpful to explore children creative imagination (NCF, 2005). Instead of passive

receiver children can take part in the process to reproduce or add in the content with the help of digital technology. It is effective tool to engage students in meaningful learning process. Students benefit from an exciting learning experience when technology is used in the classroom, which helps them to focus the learning material.

Digital technology should not be seen in a limited use as source of information only. For school education this technology should accommodate thinking process of child. Today maximum population is using digital devices from computer to mobile and digital watch. Children get exposed to digital device in their early age. Use of computer, laptop, tablets and mobile are common now. When child is oriented with digital devices before attending school itself, then the learning method of child is driven by technology.

“The introduction of new technology-assisted learning tools such as mobile devices, smartboards, MOOCs, tablets, laptops, simulations, dynamic visualisations, and virtual laboratories have altered education in schools and institutions” (Haleem et al., 2022).

The immediate learning environment, quicker evaluations, and greater involvement are not features of traditional classroom learning. There is need of wholistic approach at school level for the use of digital technology. Either its classroom processes, admission process, daily school activities, cultural and literary activities, time-table, instruction, submissions, library, labs, meetings, interaction with teachers and other school officials this need to infuse with online and offline digital tools. The active participation on digital platform from students, parents and school staff save time, energy and other resources. Nowadays almost everyone is present on social media.

Diverse society and Digital Technology

“A more social and inclusive model of learning only takes place if the appropriate context has been created” (Sparks, 2019). Atmosphere of learning is blocked by socio-economic situations. Identities like male or female, caste, religion, region, and language create hurdle to take education. These difficulties of learning can be overcome by the use of technology. Artificial intelligence doesn't discriminate learners based on their socio-cultural and economic identities. Effective use of technology can bring change in learning process.

Effective in distanced learning

Out of 17 Sustainable Development Goals given by UNESCO (2017) the dedicated goal no. 04 asked to “ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all”. Lifelong learning for all is possible when quality education is reachable to all in interactive way. As per Millenium Development Goal report 2015 the number of children out from

the primary education decreased around half from 100 million in 2000 to 57 million in 2015. After introduction of Millenium Development Goals (MDGs) there is improvement in the enrolment across the world, but still there is huge gap between the school education and quality school education. This gap is due to financial capacity, rural urban gap, and social divisions. Only human intervention alone will not be enough to fill this gap therefore there will be need of technology integrated approach to take education to each child.

Digital pedagogy and classroom instruction have merged more in recent years. Schools are looking into ways to integrate digital tools into their curricula in order to improve learning outcomes. As a result way of teaching learning transformed by digital technologies.

The study and application of modern digital technologies in teaching and learning is known as digital pedagogy. It can be used in traditional, hybrid, and online classroom settings with the goal of giving students more effective and interesting learning opportunities. The utilisation of digital content and multimedia resources, as well as the incorporation of interactive technologies and social media platforms, are just a few examples of the practices that make up digital pedagogy.

There are numerous advantages for integrating digital pedagogy into classroom instruction for both students and teachers. Students may find learning to be more enjoyable and engaging with digital tools, which can also aid in understanding and memory consolidation. Students can learn at their own pace and in their own style with the use of digital tools like adaptive learning and artificial intelligence, which can analyse student data and deliver customised feedback. High-quality education is now accessible to anybody with an internet connection, regardless of their geography or socioeconomic status, thanks to private and government online platforms.

Digital pedagogy can offer new opportunities for teachers to improve education and evaluation. Through quizzes, message boards, and online peer review can deliver more genuine and relevant assessments, resulting in a more comprehensive picture of a student's development. Additionally, using digital technologies can make administrative work easier, such grading and student record-keeping, freeing up teachers to concentrate more on education and feedback.

The government of India has created online platforms to facilitate all stakeholders of school education like, PM-E VIDYA, DIGITAL INDIA, DIKSHA, SWAYAM, NISHTHA, VIRTUAL LABS, NROER REPOSITORY, E-PATHSHALA, ICT curriculum. Social media and education app platforms like whatsapp, facebook, twitter, zoom meeting app, google meet app, google classroom

app and many more applications have revolutionized learning. The major task is to blend various methods offline and online to create understanding among learners. Competency based learning outcomes as suggested by NEP (2020), draft of new National Curriculum Framework will be possible only when pedagogy is interactive and inclusive. NEP (2020) focuses on experiential learning through “hands-on learning, arts-integrated and sports-integrated education, story-telling-based pedagogy”. Digital pedagogy works best for learning in school when it is integrated with community, art and skills.

Challenges of digital technology in school education:

Digital technology has also brought about new difficulties for society. Due to the online collection and sharing of personal data, privacy and security issues have been brought up. Digital pedagogy does have its drawbacks and difficulties, though, just like any other technology. Existing inequities in education may be made worse by the digital divide, when certain students due to network facility, purchase capacity, or any other socio-economic reason, lack the access to technology or internet connectivity. Education possibilities may be unequal due to the digital divide and unequal access to technology. There is also possibility that students may get addicted with screen time which also cause biological and psychological issues among children. Some issues with eyes vision, memory loss have been found by researchers. The extreme dependency on online and readymade resources can create habit of copying rather than creating own notes. The validity and dependability of content found online, as well as the possibility of academic fraud and cheating, are further issues that need to be addressed.

Digital technology integration into the classroom, however, also comes with some difficulties. To successfully incorporate digital tools into their teaching practices, teachers may also need help and training. Additionally, it can be challenging to determine the dependability and quality of digital and online resources, necessitating cautious review and selection by teachers.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, digital pedagogy has the potential to revolutionize education and increase the accessibility, personalization, and engagement of learning. The demands of different learners can be met via more effective and efficient learning experiences that educators can design by utilizing digital tools and platforms. To make sure that all students can benefit from these developments, it is crucial to approach digital pedagogy critically and to address the issues and constraints of technology. A powerful weapon that can influence the direction of education and open doors for students everywhere is digital technology-based pedagogy.

The way students learn and teachers teach could change, if digital pedagogy is implemented in the classroom. Blending of digital technology should create a healthy learning ecosystem. Educators and teachers may design more effective and efficient learning experiences that cater to the demands of a varied student body and enhance educational outcomes by utilising digital tools and platforms. To guarantee that across their social, racial, regional and economic identities all students can benefit from these advancements, it is crucial to address the difficulties and constraints posed by technology.

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